

Extracting Fault Features From A Helical Gear Failure Using Vibration Analysis Based On The Time-Frequency Technique

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Abstract

The gear-bearing system experiences multiple defects as a result of a little incipient flaw in the gear and bearing, resulting in catastrophic failure. The new research aims to look into a more complex issue including a transmission with a compound gear-bearing problem. Vibration measurements are taken at varied speeds and loads in order to increase the diagnostic process' effectiveness. New compound fault features are introduced in this paper, which are generated from continuous and discontinuous wavelet transforms of vibration signals. It is proposed that time–frequency domain features be employed for compound fault diagnosis, with the diagnostic power of these features compared to features retrieved from the time and frequency domains. The accuracy of these features in fault classification is higher than that of the traditional time and frequency domain parameters, according to the findings.

Introduction

The most significant and critical machine components in the condition monitoring process for rotating machineries such as gearboxes in cars, machine tools, aircraft, turbines, and other similar applications are the gears and bearings. One of the most prevalent causes of machine failure is a problem with the gears or bearings[1]. A substantial amount of mechanical system wear is caused by bearing and shock load failures, as well as pitting failures of gears. To avoid catastrophic failure, a maintenance engineer performing condition-based maintenance must be able to identify gear and bearing problems[2]. The majority of current research on this topic is on gear or bearing fault diagnosis. In addition, methods such as adaptive spectral kurtosis and spectrogram, as well as time-frequency methods, are utilized to detect many defects at the same time. There's a chance the problem is in both the gear and the bearing, resulting in a compound transmission defect, necessitating the adoption of a trustworthy diagnosis procedure [3-5].

The main purpose of these procedures is to cut down on the amount of time and money spent on equipment maintenance while also ensuring their success. These techniques have been shown to

be exceedingly time-consuming and require the intervention of a topic specialist in order to make a decision. As a result, it is necessary to build a methodology that is simple to understand and can be applied successfully and automatically to provide a solution to this problem. A methodology for detecting compound faults based on statistical attributes is presented in this work for consideration. The vibration signature of the gear will be modified if the bearing fails, and vice versa. When diagnosing a specific bearing or gear issue on a single bearing or gear, diagnostic devices are capable of generating inaccurate results. In reality, both the gear and the bearing may fail, necessitating the extraction of statistical features from the vibration signal capable of detecting multiple compound problems. Investigating numerous faults in both the gear and the bearing at the same time is a more complex process. Two types of approaches are used to find problems in machinery. The first is a visual examination by trained personnel, and the second is feature extraction and categorization using artificial intelligence. The breadth of a bearing groove race defect can be identified using wavelet decomposition techniques, according to Singh and Kumar[6-10].

Gear Defects:

- Tooth breakage is the most dangerous type of gear failure, since it disables the drive and causes shattered tooth fragments to destroy other gearbox components such as the shaft, bearing, and so on. As shown in Figure 1.1, tooth breakage can occur as a result of overload, collision, or damage.
- Pitting is a type of surface fatigue failure in gear teeth. Figure 1.2 depicts typical tooth pitting damage caused by contact stress that exceeds the fatigue tolerance limit. With repetitive load fluctuations, small portions of metal on the tooth surface fatigue and fall off over time.
- Insufficient or incorrect lubrication, overloading, and misalignment can all cause the lubricant coating to break down, allowing direct metal-on-metal contact, as shown in Figure 1.3. High temperatures and local welding of mating surfaces could result. As the gear turns, the welded patches separate, causing more problems.
- The welding process that transfers metal particles from one tooth to its match tooth is referred to as adhesive wear.
- Wear is caused by abrasive particles in the meshing area. Localized and spread gear faults both produce transmission errors and elevated vibration levels. Localized faults are more important in terms of CM, notably tooth fracture, which can occur rapidly and cause catastrophic failure in systems such as helicopters.

Fig (a): Tooth Breakage

Fig(b): Tooth Pitting

Fig(c): Tooth Scoring

Fig(d): Tooth Wear

Experimental Setup:

The motor and gearbox were mounted on the base. Figure 5.1 is the schematic diagram showing the key structural features of the rig.

Figure 5.1- Photograph of the experimental test rig

The AC motor's output shaft is mechanically coupled to the gearbox's input shaft to convey mechanical power to the gearbox and its downstream devices. Two flanges integrated to the motor housing and gearbox casing bolt the motor and gearbox together. Because of its compact design, the entire system can be put in a variety of circumstances where space is limited, such as in marine transmission[11]. Furthermore, alternative gear sets can be simply switched in this research by unbolting the two flanges that provide access to the inside of the gearbox. The mechanical power is transferred to the motor via a centre shaft supported by two bearing supports. The resistor bank consumes the electricity generated by the motor. The AC motor collects electric power from the supply system via a control cabinet that generates mechanical power and a motor that converts mechanical power back into electricity in this configuration[12]. Different loads can be applied to the system by adjusting the resistance values.

Common Gear Materials:

Gears can be built of a variety of materials, including steel, brass, bronze, cast iron, ductile iron, aluminium, powdered metals, and polymers, among others. Overall, steel is the most frequent material, however this has changed over time. In our experience, there are three factors that are most significant when choosing a gear material, at a high level. They are strength, durability, and cost, which include both the material and manufacturing costs.

Mild steel is a type of carbon steel with a low carbon content – it's also known as "low carbon steel." Although ranges vary depending on the source, the amount of carbon in mild steel is typically 0.05 percent to 0.25 percent by weight, whereas higher carbon steels are typically described as having a carbon[13].

Because their hardened surfaces increased their strength and wear resistance, helical gears manufactured of low alloy carbon steel are commonly employed as power transmission components in automobiles. EN8 is an unalloyed medium carbon steel that is used in applications where better properties than mild steel are required but the costs do not justify the purchase of a steel alloy. EN8 is an unalloyed medium carbon steel that is used in applications where better properties than mild steel are required but the costs do not justify the purchase of a steel alloy. By using flame or induction hardening techniques, EN8 can be heat treated to provide an excellent surface hardness and moderate wear resistance[14].

Specifications of Gear:

Sl No.	Particular	Details
1.	Module	1.5mm
2.	No. of teeth of Pinion	30
3.	No. of teeth of gear	90
4.	Helix Angle	15 ⁰
5.	Face width	12mm

6.	PCD of Pinion	68mm
7.	PCD of Gear	208mm
8.	Centre Distance	138mm

Results:

The next stages are separated into the results produced according to the fault conditions: 5.1 Single Tooth Damage One of the time waveforms for single tooth fault is shown in graph 1.

Time Waveform for a Single Tooth Damaged Pinion at 300 RPM

In this graph, the waveform is represented by the vertical axis displaying the acceleration curve and the horizontal axis plotting time. When a single tooth in a pinion with 17 teeth is lost, the injured tooth comes into contact with the mating gear once per revolution, therefore the peak is visible once every revolution. The pinion, on the other hand, rotates at the same rate as the input shaft, which is 300 revolutions per minute. When this speed is translated to revolutions per second, the pinion's frequency of rotation is 5 Hz (Hz). It signifies that the pinion spins at a rate of five revolutions per second. This indicates that one pinion revolution takes (1/5) second, or 0.2 second. It also implies that every 0.2 seconds, the one broken tooth will make contact with the mating gear. As a result of the damage, the amount of vibration acceleration increases throughout the meshing period (Rusmir et al, 2011). We may conclude that time waveform analysis is the most effective technique of identifying gear tooth degeneration. The DEWEsoft X1 software has the ability to transform a time waveform into a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) spectrum. This option transforms sections of the problematic pinion's graphs into FFT power spectrums, which are then compared to the healthy pinion's FFT spectrums to calculate the FFT difference. The

comparison is carried out with the help of a Microsoft PowerPoint feature. The first FFT is transparent, and the second is placed on top of it. For comparison, graphs 2(a) and 2(b) show the FFT (b). When the number of teeth in a single damaged pinion is compared to the number of teeth in a healthy pinion, the number of teeth in the single damaged pinion varies. As a result, a problematic pinion should have 16 teeth, whereas a good pinion should have 17 teeth. The FFT power spectrum reaches its apex at Gear Mesh Frequency. The peak recorded for a healthy pinion at its GMF is higher than the peak measured for a damaged pinion at its GMF in all three cases described below. This is caused by a change in the number of teeth, which is caused by a change in GMF. The GMF peak might be difficult to identify due to the large number of peaks in the FFT spectrum. Because of the various loads in a system, it is hard to detect the peak of GMF if the load rapidly increases at a frequency near to the GMF frequency[15-19].

(a) At 600 rpm

(b) At 900 rpm

Graph 2 FFT power spectrums

5.2 Teeth Damage on Both Sides

A double tooth on a 17-tooth pinion with two peaks appears at the end of each revolution because the damage occurs twice in a rotation with the mating gear when the double tooth is damaged. However, in the experimental situation, the input shaft rotates at a speed of 300 rpm, which implies that the pinion likewise rotates at a speed of 300 rpm. This speed is converted to revolutions per second, which results in a frequency of rotation of the pinion of 5 hertz (Hz). In a single second, the pinion will revolve five times. This means that the pinion completes one revolution in one-fifth of a second, or in 0.2 second overall. It also means that the two damaged teeth will make contact with the mating gear once every 0.2 seconds, which is a significant amount of time. In this case, the peak may be detected every 0.1 second since the two injured teeth are precisely opposite each other. At the moment of meshing, the damage causes an increase in the amplitude of the vibration to occur. The similar phenomena is seen in Graph 3. (Rusmir, et al, 2011).

Graph 3 Time Waveform for Double Teeth Damaged Pinion at 300 rpm

(b) At 900 rpm

Graph 4 FFT Power Spectrums

There is a difference in the number of teeth between the double teeth damaged pinion and the healthy pinion due to the two damaged teeth. As a result, it is assumed that a problematic pinion

has 15 teeth and a healthy pinion has 17 teeth. At Gear Mesh Frequency, the peak can be seen in FFT.

Conclusions :

Following a study of the graphs, tables, and findings, several conclusions were drawn.

1) The damaged tooth meshes with the matching gear once every revolution, resulting in a single-tooth damaged pinion rotating at 300 revolutions per minute (5 Hz). Because the pinion spins at a frequency of 5 Hz, or 5 revolutions per second, one pinion rotation takes (1/5) second to complete. As the injured tooth interacts with the adjacent teeth, it has a major effect on the succeeding teeth. As a result, the peak is seen every 0.2 seconds.

2) The damaged teeth mesh twice every revolution with the corresponding gear, resulting in a double-toothed damaged pinion rotating at 300 revolutions per minute (5 Hz). Because the pinion spins at a frequency of 5 Hz, or 5 revolutions per second, one pinion rotation takes (1/5) second to complete. As the injured tooth interacts with the adjacent teeth, it has a major effect on the succeeding teeth. As a consequence, the peak emerges approximately every 0.2 seconds. Graph 3 shows a peak every 0.1 second. As a result of this, it is possible to identify defects such as single and double tooth damage simply by analysing the time waveform and speed.

3) As seen in table 2 and graph 6, the amplitude of the RMS value and variance are larger for a worn pinion than for a healthy pinion. Numerous computational methods, such as the root mean square error and variance, can be used to detect problems such as wear.

4) In graph 7 and table 3, the RMS value and variance of a single tooth damaged pinion are compared to those of a double tooth damaged pinion. The magnitude of the RMS value and variation for double tooth damage are larger based on this data. Additionally, it suggests that computational approaches such as the root mean square error and variance are used to estimate the severity of the problem.

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